

COLLECTORS. (OBJECT CONTAINERS).

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ANNOTATION.

This article provides information about collectors, that is, object containers in the JAVA programming language. In addition, he provided information about the vector collector and special methods.

Enter

So cases will be you your problem the solution for of objects which quantity need you you don't know or to you objects to arrays than more suitable in appearance storage need

This without JAVA such problems the solution for 4 class – collector present is enough. These are –

vector, Bitfer, Stack and Hashtalle. Collectors in application shortcoming is that the object

to the collector when adding object own type about information loses. This therefore for

happened gives that collectors of objects global containers will be therefore for they are

to themselves adding object types attention does not give That's it because of collector current object type Object type replaces because this class of JAVA everyone classes for root class will be Collector inside object type about information change because of this objects in application them right

type change need

Vector collector.

Vector class apply very simple this class object is made the object Vector to to add add for Element () class style is applied. Then, to the object appeal to do for element At ()

style is applied. First style for parameter as adding object, in the second object index is displayed. Size () style collector inside of objects maximum the amount

returns

Enumeration – collector iterator

Enumeration – Vector from higher level collector

Vector element `At ( )` class style supporting desired at the time desired to the object appeal to do

possible Collector of Enumeration such style no and Enumeration inside free

to objects appeal to do permission does not give Enumeration collector those inside element `( )` style using `get` possible. To objects next `Element( )` of the first to call of the collector the first object will give. In Enumeration collector inside

objects quantity about not to worry possible More `Element ( )` using the method enough she is current object the last one if not, to the boulevard true the meaning returns reflection without – false.

`BitSet` collector.

A `BitSet` collector is like a `Vector`, but only holds values of one bit size. This collector is convenient to use as a flag container . `BitSet` is the minimum of the collector

size is 64 bits, which means that using this collector to store less than 64 bits of data will not be efficient. `BitSet` has methods `set ( )` to set the flag, `clear ( )` to remove the flag, and `size ( )` to determine the size of the collector.

Collector `Stack.Stack` collector works as "last – in first - out" (LIFO), that is, when accessing the collector

the last added object is displayed first.

The `push ( )` method is used to add an object to the stack , and to retrieve an object from the stack

`pop ( )` method is used. The `Empty ( )` method returns a boolean value, if true, the `Stack` is empty

is determined. Since `Stack` is a daughter class of the `Vector` class, the `Element At ( )` and `add Element ( )` methods of the `Vector` collector also work on the `Stack` collector.

`Hashtable` collector. `Hashtable` collector as a collection of objects object group in a specific measure (keys)

It is convenient to use when you need to work on. To implement a `Hashtable` collector

An object of the `Hashtable` class is created, with collector methods for working with collector objects

is applied. The `size ( )` method returns the number of elements in the collection, objects in the collection

otherwise the is Empty () method returns true to boolean, put (Object key, Object value)

method adds an element to the collection where value is the key, we to the collection

The key object you want to store is the get(Object key) method corresponding to the key value

(object) returns and the remove(Object key) method returns the key from the collection and its corresponding removes the object .

References:

1. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). RSA VA EL-GAMAL OCHIQ KALITLI SHIFRLASH ALGORITMI ASOSIDA ELEKTRON RAQMLI IMZOLARI. RSA OCHIQ KALITLI SHIFRLASH ALGORITMI ASOSIDAGI ELEKTRON RAQAMLI IMZO. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 316-319.
2. Sharopova, M. M. qizi . (2023). JAVA TILI YORDAMIDA OB'EKTGA YUNALTIRILGAN DASTURLASH ASOSLARI BILAN TANISHISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 111-119.
3. Sharopova, M. (2023). CHOOSE: COMPOSITION OR INHERITANCE. Science and innovation in the education system, 2(13), 96-102.
4. Sharopova, M. (2023). JAVA PROGRAMMING IN THE LANGUAGE HERITAGE TO DO SYNTAX. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 2(12), 82-87.
5. Sharopova, M. (2023). ARRAY AND ARRAYS INSTALLATION. Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences, 2(12), 102-107.
6. Sharopova, M. (2023). CLASSES AGAIN APPLY. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 2(13), 106-111.
7. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). INTRODUCING" PROGRAM CONTROL OPERATORS" IN THE JAVA PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 222-231.
8. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). Working with folders in the JAVA programming language. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 232-236.
9. Latipova, S. S. qizi . (2024). CAPUTO MA'NOSIDAGI KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO'YICHA TO'G'RI MASALALAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 375-382.

10. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). BETA FUNKSIYA XOSSALARI VA BU FUNKSIYA YORDAMIDA TURLI MASALALARNI YECHISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 66-76.
11. Latipova, S. S. qizi . (2024). KASR TARTIBLI ODDIY DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 383-390.
12. Latipova, S. S. qizi . (2024). GAMMA FUNKSIYA. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 391-399.
13. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). SOLVING THE INVERSE PROBLEM OF FINDING THE SOURCE FUNCTION IN FRACTIONAL ORDER EQUATIONS. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
14. Latipova, S. S. (2023). SOLVING THE INVERSE PROBLEM OF FINDING THE SOURCE FUNCTION IN FRACTIONAL ORDER EQUATIONS. Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal, 1(10), 13-23.
15. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). HEAT PHYSICAL MEANING AND ORIGIN OF DIFFUSION EQUATIONS. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
16. daughter Latipova, S. S. (2023). HEAT PHYSICAL MEANING AND ORIGIN OF DIFFUSION EQUATIONS. World of Scientific news in Science, 1(2), 163-176.
17. Shahnoza, L. (2023, March). KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA VA BOSHLANG'ICH FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO'YICHA TESKARI MASALALAR. In " Conference on Universal Science Research 2023" (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 8-10).
18. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). RIMAN-LUIVILL KASR TARTIBLI INTEGRALI VA HOSILASIGA OID AYRIM MASALALARNING ISHLANISHI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(12), 216-220.
19. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). MITTAG-LIFFLER FUNKSIYASI VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 238-244.
20. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). KASR TARTIBLI HOSILA TUSHUNCHASI. SCHOLAR, 1(31), 263-269.
- 21.
22. Boboqulova, M. X. (2023). STOMATOLOGIK MATERIALLARNING FIZIK-MEXANIK XOSSALARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 223-228.
23. Xamroyevna, B. M. (2023). ORGANIZM TO 'QIMALARINING ZICHLIGINI ANIQLASH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 50-58.
24. Khamroyevna, M. B. (2023). PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF BIOLOGICAL MEMBRANES, BIOPHYSICAL MECHANISMS OF MOVEMENT OF

- SUBSTANCES IN THE MEMBRANE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 217-221.
25. Bobokulova, M. K. (2023). IMPORTANCE OF FIBER OPTIC DEVICES IN MEDICINE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 212-216.
26. Mukhtaram Bobokulova Khamroyevna. (2023). Radiation Protection. Dosimetry . Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science, 4(6), 134-139.
27. Bobokulova, M. K. (2024). TOLALI OPTIKA ASBOBLARINING TIBBIYOTDAGI AHAMIYATI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 517-524.
28. Axmedova, Z. I. (2023). LMS TIZIMIDA INTERAKTIV ELEMENTLARNI YARATISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(11), 368-372.
29. Axmedova, Z. (2023). MOODLE TIZIMI VA UNING IMKONIYATLARI. Development and innovations in science, 2(11), 29-35.
30. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). USING THE USEFUL ASPECTS OF THE MOODLE SYSTEM AND ITS POSSIBILITIES. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 201-205.
31. Zulxumor, A. (2022). IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERACTIVE COURSES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. ILMIY TADQIQOT VA INNOVATSIYA, 1(6), 128-132.
32. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). SQL (STRUCTURED QUERY LANGUAGE) STATISTICAL PACKAGES OF CAPABILITIES. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 2(12), 781-787.
33. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). SQL (STRUCTURED QUERY LANGUAGE) CAPABILITIES OF THE STATISTICAL DATABASE LANGUAGE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 274-280.
34. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). CREATION AND PLACEMENT OF INTERACTIVE ELEMENTS. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 2(13), 120-128.
35. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS, ELECTRONIC EDUCATION: TASKS AND OPPORTUNITIES. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(21), 171-177.
36. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). DISADVANTAGES OF ELECTRONIC LEARNING. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 2(12), 99-109.
37. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). SQL SPECIFICATIONS FOR DATA ANALYSIS. Science and innovation in the education system, 2(13), 113-120.

38. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). Programming Environments for Creating Mobile Applications on the Android Operating System. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 305-309.
39. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. li.(2023). Mobil ilovalar yaratish va ularni bajarish jarayoni. International journal of scientific researchers, 2(2).
40. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. (2023). USE OF ARTIFICIAL NERVOUS SYSTEMS IN MODELING. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 269-273.
41. Behruz Ulugbek og, Q. (2023). TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE: A DYNAMIC PARTNERSHIP. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(11).
42. Quvvatov, B. U. o'g'li . (2023). ALEXNET - TASVIRLARNI TASNIFLASH UCHUN KONVOLYUTSION NEYRON TARMOQ. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 77–90.
43. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g'li Quvvatov. (2023). MAXIMUM PRINCIPLE AND ERROR ANALYSIS. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 480–486.
44. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). CAPUTA MA'NOSIDA KASR TARTIBLI HOSILALAR VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 360-365.
45. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). MAXSUS SOHALARDA KARLEMAN MATRITSASI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 137-141.
46. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). APPROXIMATION OF FUNCTIONS WITH COEFFICIENTS. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 135–138.
47. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). Applications of the double integral to mechanical problems. International journal of sciearchers,2(2), 101-103.
48. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). FINDING THE MAXIMUM AND MINIMUM VALUE OF A FUNCTION ON A SEGMENT. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 245-248.
49. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). FUNKSIYALARNI KOEFFITSIENTLAR ORQALI FUNKSIYALARNI YAKINLASHTIRISH HAQIDA MA'LUMOTLAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 102–110.
50. Sharipova, M. (2023, December). RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN STRAIGHT LINES AND PLANES IN SPACE. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 2, No. 12, pp. 60-66).
51. Sharipova, M. (2023). FRACTIONAL DERIVATIVES. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(27), 106-113.

52. Sharipova, M. (2023). CORRECT PLACED AND CORRECT NOT PLACED ISSUES. *Models and methods in modern science*, 2(13), 115-121.
53. Sharipova, M. (2023). HEAT SPREAD EQUATION. *Инновационные исследования в науке*, 2(12), 50-56.
54. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). HIGH MATH SCORE AND INTERVAL ASSESSMENT. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(10), 420–424.
55. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). IN HIGHER MATHEMATICS, THE EXTREMUM OF A MULTIVARIABLE FUNCTION. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(10), 425–429.
56. Sharipova, M. P. (2024). ISSIQLIK TARQALISH TENGLAMASI UCHUN KOSHI MASALASI. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 2(1), 525–532.
57. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). Zamonaviy ta’limda axborot texnologiyalari va ularni qo’llash usul va vositalari. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(11), 481-486.
58. Муродов, О. Т. (2023). РАЗРАБОТКА АВТОМАТИЗИРОВАННОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ И ВЛАЖНОСТИ В ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННЫХ КОМНАТ. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(26), 91-95.
59. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA DARSLARINI TASHKIL ETISHDA INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(32), 194-201.
60. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA FANINI O’QITISHDA YANGI INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH METODIKASI. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(34), 130-139.
61. MURODOV, O. T. (2023). INNOVATIVE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND NEW METHODS AND TOOLS FOR THEIR APPLICATION IN TODAY'S EDUCATION. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(12).
62. Turakulovich, M. O. (2023). DEVELOPMENT AND INSTALLATION OF AN AUTOMATIC TEMPERATURE CONTROL SYSTEM IN ROOMS. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(12).
63. Jurakulov, S. Z. O., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). THE MAIN SIGNIFICANCE OF THE DEPARTMENTS OF PHYSICS IN THE DEVELOPMENT. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(33), 162-167.
64. Jurakulov, S. Z. O., & Turdiboyev, H. (2023). RELATIONSHIPS OF PHYSICS WITH ART IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(33), 144-147.
65. Jurakulov, S. Z. O., & Turdiboyev, H. (2023). ADVANCED STRATEGIES FOR LEARNING PHYSICS. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(33), 152-156.

66. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). IN THE EDUCATIONAL FIELD OF PHYSICS LEVEL AND POSITION. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 157-161.
67. Jurakulov, S. (2023). PROPERTIES AND CHARACTERISTICS OF NUCLEAR ENERGY. Инновационные исследования в науке, 2(12), 35-39.
68. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Hamidov, E. (2023). YADRO ENERGIYASINING XOSSA VA XUSUSIYATLARI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 182-186.
69. IN THE EDUCATIONAL FIELD OF PHYSICS LEVEL AND POSITION
70. SZ Jurakulov, O Nurboyev - GOLDEN BRAIN, 2023
71. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Turdiboyev, X. (2023). FIZIKA FANINI O 'RGANISHNING YUQORI DARAJADAGI STRATEGIYALAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 152-156.
72. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Turdiboyev, X. (2023). TA'LIM SOHASIDA FIZIKANING SAN'AT BILAN ALOQALARI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 144-147.
73. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). FIZIKA FANINING BO 'LIMLARINING RIVOJLANISHDAGIDAGI ASOSIY AHAMIYATI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 162-167.
74. Jurakulov, S. (2023). ON THE RELATION OF METAPHYSICS TO PHYSICS. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(27), 9-20.
75. Jurakulov, S. (2023). ON THE RELATION OF METAPHYSICS TO PHYSICS. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(27), 9-20.
76. Jurakulov, S. (2023). IMPACT OF THE MINING INDUSTRY ON PEOPLE AND THE ENVIRONMENT. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(21), 143-150.
77. Jurakulov, S. (2023). CHANGES IN LANGUAGE DUE TO NEW PHYSICS. Models and methods in modern science, 2(13), 77-87.
78. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). СОЗДАНИЕ ПРОГРАММЫ ДЛЯ ИМИТАЦИИ ШИФРОВАНИЯ МАШИНЫ ENIGMA НА ЯЗЫКЕ PYTHON. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(5), 317-323.
79. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). STUDY THE PSYCHOLOGY OF PROGRAMMERS. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 563-568.
80. Tursunov, B. J., & Allanazarov, G. O. (2019). Perspektivnye tehnologii proizvodstva po uluchsheniyu kachestva benzina. Theory and practice of contemporary science, 3(45), 305-308.
81. Турсунов, Б. Ж., & Алланазаров, Г. О. (2019). Перспективные технологии производства по улучшению качества бензина. Теория и практика современной науки, (3 (45)), 305-308.

82. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). Analysis of Concepts About the Effect of an Explosion in Solid Wednesday. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 296-304.
83. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). Methods of Control of Explosion Energy Distribution in Rocks. Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies (2993-2599), 1(10), 108-117.
84. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). WASTE-FREE TECHNOLOGY FOR ENRICHMENT OF PURIFIC COPPER-ZINC ORE. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 288-293.
85. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). ANALYSIS OF MODERN METHODS FOR OIL SLUDGE PROCESSING. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 280-287.
86. Jumaev, K., & Tursunov, B. (2022, December). Environmentally friendly technology for obtaining fuel briquettes from oil waste. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 1112, No. 1, p. 012005). IOP Publishing.
87. Ахмедова, О. Б., Турсунов, Б. Ж., & угли Худойбердиев, Н. Н. (2022). Анализ физико-химических свойств нефтешламов Бухарского НПЗ и рациональные способы их утилизации. Science and Education, 3(6), 495-507.
88. Турсунов, Б. Д. (2016). Анализ и выявление путей совершенствования процессов горного дела. Молодой ученый, (23), 105-106.

